

Inclusive Education Issues and Challenges of Inclusive Education

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Abstract:- Inclusive education has a collaborative and respectful school culture.

Inclusive education faces many challenges and problems.

Inclusive education is taking steps to overcome many problems of education.

The challenges facing inclusive education are divided in to 4 categories.

Attitudinal Barriers.

Social Barriers.

Infrastructural Barriers.

Economic Barriers.

- **Social and curricular adoption**
Making all options of education.

Developing strategies for meeting the education.

The curriculum should meet all the requirements of inclusive education.

Achieving national integrity through curriculum. Developing good learning and good teaching practice.

Making the flexible an accessible curriculum. Adopting needful strategies.

Utilizing technology and assistive devices.

Providing vocational education.

Teachers training in Inclusive education.

Prioritizing practical aspects.

practical.

The School board should provide resources to support inclusive education.

- **Evaluation Procedures**
Assessment of knowledge and skills in inclusive classroom

Formal and informal assessment

Change weighting scale

Allow for self-assessment

Provide multiple text formats.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching process is multidimensional process. Inclusive education meets the needs of all students. Inclusive education is educating all student in education. Inclusive education is a means of achieving the objectives of education. Inclusive education is way for the underprivileged to utilize their opportunities unlike general education. Inclusive education aims to mainstream all learners. In the Indian context there are many difficulties in getting opportunities education. There are possibilities for inclusive education to expand its scope efforts should be made to enhance all capacities of the community through inclusive education.

The concept of inclusive education is a process of education which ensures the equal participation of all children in teaching learning process. Inclusive education also called inclusion is education that includes everyone. The scope of inclusive education is very vast. It covers a wide area of content as follows.

• Scope of inclusive education

- Children with disability
- Children in remote tribal area
- Working children
- Children with HIV/AIDS and other chronic illness
- Children of migrant labor
- Street children
- Girls living in difficult circumstance
- All other children

• Issues and challenges of inclusive education

- Inclusive education facing many issues and challenges in achieving its commitment:
- Barriers of inclusive education
- School and curricular adoption
- Teacher Training
- Evaluation

II. BARRIERS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The role of teacher and parents are very important. Because positive attitude results in positive impact. Negative attitude results in negative impact.

A. Attitudinal barriers

Attitudinal barriers include many attitude related problems like,

- Lack of skills
- Physical and emotional disabilities
- Negative attitudes
- Stereotyped

- Lack of interest
- Lack of awareness

B. *Social barriers*

- Social discrimination
- Social rigidity
- Sexual abuse
- Religious belief
- Culture
- Caste
- Parents' ignorance

C. *Infrastructural barrier*

- Lack of facility
- Institutional Barrier
- Lack of School
- Inadequate facility
- Lack of literature
- Rural and remote areas

D. *Educational barriers*

- Lack of trained teacher
- Rigid curriculum
- Language difficulty
- Communication barrier
- Examination system
- Basic facility
- School Environment

E. *Economic Barriers*

- Poverty
- Lack of infrastructure
- Rural areas
- Disabled population
- Lack of finance
- Lack of transport facilities

III. SCHOOL AND CURRICULAR ADAPTATION

School and curricular adaptation is the most important aspects of inclusive education. The learning goals outlined in the curriculum are promoted and pupil well-being and engagement are prioritized. School and curricular is part of effective teaching and learning.

- Making all options of education.
- Developing strategies for meeting the education.
- The curriculum should meet all the requirements of inclusive education.
- Achieving national integrity through curriculum.
- Developing good learning and good teaching practice.
- Making the flexible and accessible curriculum.
- Providing necessary TLM for different disabled children.
- Adopting needful strategies.
- Utilizing technology and assistive devices.
- Organizing activities to suits.
- Developing appropriate assessment and evaluation procedures.
- Providing vocational training facilities.
- Conducting.
- Barrier free intervention.

IV. TEACHERS TRAINING IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Teachers provide a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students are valued as integral member of the classroom and community.

• **Role of teacher in inclusive education**

- Curriculum design
- Classroom instruction
- Learning assessments
- Advocating of students
- Understand their role in supporting all learners
- Create and nature inclusive learning environments.
- Identify the strengths and needs of the learners
- Choose adaptations that support students, social, emotional behavioral and academic strength and needs
- Planning instruction for the class as well as individual students
- Classroom management
- Collaborative problems activities.
- Accommodate inclusion students.
- Provision of special facilities meeting the personal needs.
- Adaptation of authentic assessment.

V. EVALUATION PROCEDURES ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN INCLUSIVE CLASS ROOM

Evaluation is also challenge in inclusive education. It is ongoing activities that allow students and instructors to understand student progress on meeting the course learning objectives. Teachers should provide democratic environment to students and expressing the view of the students.

A. *Formal and informal Assessment*

The schools assessments policy is learner focused and outlines purpose/use of assessment, roles and responsibilities of those involved. Links between assessment and outcomes. Planning for teaching and learning and opportunities for peer and self assessment.

B. *Change evaluation techniques*

When calculating a final grade for report card, teachers use student assignments, tests, quizzes and exams collect over the semester. Each type of assessment holds a certain weight in the overall grade.

C. Providing opportunity for self assessment

Give students an opportunity to assess their own learning and reflect on the progress they are making. They can identify their own gaps in skills or knowledge, revise their work and set realistic goals.

D. Providing various resources of the technology

Tests do not need to be restricted to pencil and paper formats. Students with written output issues can be given oral response tests. Teachers can use multiple choice, long answer, short answer diagrams, charts, fill in the blank and other graphic organizers to have students answer questions about material.

Teachers employ formative and summative assessment approaches that are flexible, matched to the ability of the pupils and are age and curriculum appropriate.

Teachers are competent to administer and interpret a range of assessment materials including standardized tests.

E. Assessment of knowledge and skill inclusive classroom

Assessment is an integral part of every classroom and can sometimes become quite a daunting task inclusive assessment is about more than evaluating students. It is the ongoing activities that allow students and instructors to understand student progress on meeting the course learning objectives. Students should be asked to demonstrate their learning through formative and summative assessments.

F. Criteria in assessing the performance of disabled children

- Emphasis only on performance and progress but not for marks to score
- Have in mind that that child should feel to co-up with mainstream
- Do not compare one with other disability children
- Scope given speech, music, songs, etc for visually disabled
- Identify the support each child needs to progress individually.

VI. CONCLUSION

Inclusive Education is facing many challenges. There are many solutions to solve these problems. The main problems inclusive education is the lack of connection between the problem and the solution. Teacher should apply this linking function. Organizational attitudes of teachers should be formed in solving all these problems. Addressing the challenges of inclusive education requires overcoming all the difficulties from curriculum to assessment.

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